

From Academics To Ethics – The Transformative Role Of The Teacher

Paper Id : 20489 Submission Date : 2025-07-01 Acceptance Date : 2025-07-21 Publication Date : 2025-07-27

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.16886696

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/innovation.php#8>

Diksha Singh

M.E.D
Department Of Education
University Of Allahabad
Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh,
India

Abstract

Indian education is deeply rooted in values, with India being renowned for its value system. The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 emphasizes the Indianization of education, which is rich in values transmitted by teachers and other knowledgeable individuals such as family members, parents, elder siblings, and teachers. Among these, teachers play a crucial role as children spend a significant amount of time in school and formal education settings. This paper explores the theoretical inputs on values, the major outcomes, the role of teachers in inculcating values in their students. It also examines various factors influencing values. And the findings highlight that teachers are pivotal in value inculcation, as students often view them as role models. Therefore, it is imperative for teachers to adhere to discipline and routine, as students are likely to emulate what they observe.

Keywords

Teachers, Human Values, NEP 2020, Ethics, Moral Development.

Introduction

Values are very crucial because it construct behaviour and build ethical societies with human values like empathy, respect and integrity. These values are constructed by factor like family, society and teachers, playing crucial role as role models. Teacher foster critical thinking and ethical values and build strong moral foundations, but the efforts of teacher faces various challenges due to limited training in value-based education, negative impact of technology and western culture. This study explores how teachers promote human value, factor influencing this process and challenges they face aiming to emphasize the importance of value education in building a better future.

Value

Schwartz (2006), Values are the things that we care about in life like safety, being independent, being kind, achieving success or enjoying the life. Values are not same for everyone it depend on what's important to one person might not much effective for another person. Since 1950 researchers have been working to understand values in a better way. Many experts have said on main ideas about basic values, values are not just logical rather they are connected to our feelings, prepare to achive goals of life. Value are different from rules and opinions that is why value can be applied on many things and situations, It makes us to understand what is right? And what is wrong?

Human Value

(eGyankosh), Human values are the thought that direct people to live their life and behave in society. These values make people to understand what is right and important for them.

In a society people live together exchange their values and ideas, with the time people have changed their thought process and way of living. Changes are due to the values of communities they belong to.

Gordon W.Allport, a psychologist, identified 6 types of human values.

1. Theoretical: People who are interested in finding out the truth.
2. Economic: People who are known about what is useful in daily life.
3. Aesthetic: People who celebrate beauty and art.
4. Social: People who give more important to good citizenship and are helping for other.
5. Political: People who came to get power and control in society.
6. Religious: people whose thoughts are inclined towards spirituality|Ideal Teacher

Objective of study

1. To examine the critical role of teachers in value inculcation among students.
2. To analyse how teachers as a role model influence student's moral development.
3. To explore the factors that impact the development of human values in students such as family, culture, education and social media.
4. To identify the challenges faced by teachers in delivering value-based education in contemproyary classroom.
5. To highlight the relevance of National Education Policies and commissions in strengthening the role of teachers in moral education

Review of Literature

Ge (2023), Identified several key factors that influence that influence human values, Culture shape personal believe and it also place important role in decision making. In Chinese culture value have important place in comparison to personal benefit on the other hand in western culture they give importance to priority, personal interest and freedom. Family is responsible for shaping individual's behaviour value and character. Good family environment help in developing responsibility, kindness and good citizens. Social media has a great impact on individual by exposing them to other's opinion and social standards. The children born after 2000 praise more to Western individualism than traditional group harmony. According to marxism human values depends on society and social values expert says that individual value come from how there deeds influence society and how much satisfied they feel for oneself. Value education shapes individual's beliefs and values. Maslow suggested that education is necessary for knowledge of One's self worth. Value education helps in inculcating moral values personal values and spirituality. This makes education a key tool in helping people to grow and develop better values and here teacher play a crucial role in using the tool (education) in promoting values among their students

Main Text**Main characteristics of an ideal teacher**

Bedir (2023), Passion: Passion is prerequisite for education, because teaching requires dedication and effort.

Commitment: Teacher commitment is crucial for success of education. They focus on shaping future generations and treat their profession more than a job.

Being a role model: A good teacher act as a role model who guides students create a conducive learning environment and help to shape the future of society.

Bedir identified some personal and professional characteristics that is ready for change , build good relationships with other, respect people's value and cultures, patients and understanding, tolerant of differences, curious and eager to learn, confident and make clear decisions, selfless and caring ,energetic and motivated, treat everyone equally, respecting students, being kind and knowledgeable, appreciating the teaching profession, understanding individual differences, guiding students knowing rights and responsibilities.

Role of teacher in promoting human values

Basumatary (2024), Teachers have the major responsibility for the inculcation of values among students, which is also very important for their holistic development. The most important thing is the teacher is a role model of students and students try to imitate their teacher, so teacher must have moral values like truth, commitment, dedication, respect for other, honesty in their behaviour, they should encourage students for being rational about their thought and actions and teacher should inclined the thought process of students towards critical thinking giving them real life problems. Teachers should built good relationship with students and their respective parents, so that the work of value inculcation can be done at school and home simultaneously, also they should provide a students some extrinsic motivation in the form of appreciation and rewards for their good behaviour, these things will reinforce them in exhibiting moral values. It is responsibility of teachers to give a students the exposure of actual world and provide the chance to do public duty, community responsibility, good will and compassion. Teacher should teach students to be rational and logical, not just follow traditions. Teacher should work on improving their own personality to inspire and motivate students because students can best judge their teacher's character.

Promotion of value education by teachers

Basumatary(2024), There are several commissions and committees who have given their recommendations on value education. University Education Commission (1948-49) advised to include moral and spiritual education in curriculum. Encouraged teaching values like social responsibility discipline and integrity, Secondary Education Commission (1952-53) emphasized teaching student the importance of citizenship and social responsibility and recommended activities like debates discussion and social service to promote values, Kothari Commission (1964-66) emphasize the importance of national Unity, social harmony and democratic values also highlighted that the teachers have active role in value inculcation through their actions and interactions with students, National Policy on Education (1986) tells about the need to teach secularism, socialism, democracy and equality through education and also recommended promoting values through extra curricular activities and community services, National Education Policy (2020) focus on student's social ethical and emotional development among with their learning, also talk about importance of human values ethics and community involvement in communication.

Challenges of teachers in promoting value education:

Basumatary recognised various challenges faced by the teachers in promoting value education among students that is social media, different cultural and socio-economic background, individual Differences, lack of formal training of teachers, lack of interest of students in value related discourse.

An ideal teacher is successful in education maintain their patients in stressful situations, communicates well with others, can deal with educational problems in an effective way, play role of good guide for students and parents and they are responsible and consistent for their profession.

Methodology

It involves secondary sources such as research papers, policy documents, academic repository such as eGyankosh and peer-reviewed journals.

Research Design

This study follows a descriptive and qualitative research design, focusing on theoretical analysis and literature based exploration, policy document and theoretical perspective of role of teachers in value education.

Data Analysis Technique

Findings were drawn through synthesis of key themes such as teacher as role model, value inculcation strategies, challenges in value education, and policy recommendations.

Conclusion

The summation of study shows the pivotal role of teachers in nurturing and inculcating human values among students. Various other studies have proved that teachers are very important for value transaction among students. This study shows that various commissions and committees have given their recommendations to give importance to human values in curriculum and formal education. The outcome of study says that the teachers should portray themselves in a way that fosters moral value among students. In addition to this the teacher should encourage value of global citizenship, sense of gratitude, sense of responsibility, sense of accountability, critical thinking and decision making ability and teacher must create value based classroom environment.

The major findings of this study is the influencing factors such as family, culture, social media, and education system plays crucial role in value inculcation but the teacher remains central to this ecosystem by building a morally responsible and socially aware generation. However the existing challenges must be addressed through structured teacher education and supportive policies. Aligning with the vision of NEP 2020, the study conclude that empowering teachers with ethical clarity, pedagogical tools, and emotional intelligence is essential for nurturing human values and preparing students to become responsible global citizen.

References

1. Basumatary, M. (2024). *The role of teachers in promoting value education. International Journal of Multidisciplinary Educational Research, 13(6[3])*, 31. Sucharitha Publication. <https://www.ijmer.in>
2. Bedir, H. (2023). *Three main characteristics of an ideal teacher. International Journal of Social Sciences & Educational Studies, 10(3)*, 438. <https://doi.org/10.23918/ijsses.v10i3p438>
3. eGyanKosh. <https://egyankosh.ac.in>
4. Ge, J. (2023). *On the factors influencing human value. Advances in Education, Humanities and Social Science Research: ICSECS 2023, 7. Ningbo Foreign Language School.*
5. Schwartz, S. H. (2006). *Basic human values: An overview. In Basic human values: Theory, methods, and applications. The Hebrew University of Jerusalem*